

CHARACTERIZING, MODELING, AND VALIDATING THE PROCESSING OF OUT-OF-AUTOCLAVE ORGANIC MATRIX COMPOSITES AS A FUNCTION OF CURE CYCLE

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ABSTRACT

In this work, recent experimental and computational efforts toward predicting the processing of out-of-autoclave (OOA) organic matrix composites (OMCs) are presented. Specifically, this work details the methods to characterize the chemorheology of the resin, the models to describe the reaction kinetics and evolution of material properties, and the experimental techniques to validate the predicted residual stresses and deformations due to processing. As part of this study, a modeling approach is presented that includes: (1) novel data reduction techniques used to describe the material submodels for properties such as resin cure kinetics, viscosity, cure shrinkage, and coefficient of thermal expansion using a model form relating the properties to the glass transition temperature, and (2) a thermomechanical response model that employs a finite element unit cell model with an elastic-viscoplastic material idealization to capture the rapid changes in time-dependent residual stress caused by excursions near and beyond the glass transition temperature. The details of the experiments to calibrate the submodels – including the specimen fabrication and preparation – are presented with an emphasis on thermal analysis techniques, volumetric dilatometer measurements, and rate- and time-dependent mechanical response. The measured deformations are compared to values predicted by computational simulations performed in Abaqus using custom user material subroutines (UMATs).

1 INTRODUCTION

Early efforts to characterize residual stress and the associated dimensional changes in fiber-reinforced organic matrix composites (OMCs) focused on thermoelastic changes from a stress-free temperature [1]. In many cases, these predictions were successful, in part because of the relative simplicity of the materials, cure cycles, and geometries used at the time. The addition of chemical kinetics and property models that reflected the temperature history and state changes in the curing material (resin viscosity, cure shrinkage, and coefficient of thermal expansion) brought about improvements in these predictions [2]. Recently, significant research and development has been made to model the manufacturing of structural composites because of the potential pay-offs. For instance, new composite designs are becoming increasingly complex resulting in non-intuitive manufacturing deformations requiring significant rework or expensive trial-and-error mold tooling compensation. In addition, new advanced aerospace composite material systems, such as third generation out-of-

autoclave (OOA) systems, offer a variety of cure cycle designs including unsupported freestanding cures and postcures. This presents significant opportunities for cure cycle and throughput optimization via simulation. More sophisticated finite element analyses using viscoelastic models [3,4,5,6] do exist; however, they require extensive mechanical and thermal testing to obtain properties and data and still do not sufficiently capture the trends of the OOA freestanding postcures [7] or other complicated multi-step autoclave cure schedules where the cycle temperature tends to cross the instantaneous glass transition temperature of the material several times during the cure. The approach adopted in the current investigation is an attempt to find relatively simple and innovative model forms that can account for the effects of time-dependent chemorheology and thermomechanical behavior as the cure reactions proceed and can be applied to predict any of these complex manufacturing scenarios. This paper presents the details of the characterization experiments, measured residual stress deformations, and computational simulations as they evolve during processing of an OOA medium-tough epoxy polymer matrix composite reinforced with unidirectional intermediate modulus, continuous carbon fibers (Cycom[®] 5320-1/IM7).

2 MODELING

The proposed models described in what follows are designed to capture the effects of viscous behavior on mechanical and thermomechanical response of a curing composite, based on relatively simple models. To this end, we adopt the following two working hypotheses:

- (1) The effect of the two most important state variables in the polymer matrix, temperature and degree of cure, can be captured through the use of the *reduced temperature*,

$$T_r(T, x) = \frac{T}{T_g(x)} - 1 \quad (1)$$

in which x represents the degree of cure at a point. The viscosity and other variables are, therefore, controlled by the closeness of the temperature to the current glass transition.

- (2) The predominant effect of the low viscosity observed near the T_g is to produce local resin viscoplastic flow (unrestricted creep) that results in permanent deformation and relieves stresses accumulated at earlier times.

Models based on these hypotheses are implemented as user-supplied material subroutines (UMATs) that plug into the Abaqus finite element software [8]. The UMATs provide detailed descriptions of the chemical kinetics, heat transfer properties, mechanical response (stiffness, viscosity), thermal expansion, and cure shrinkage behavior of the composite throughout the cure process, passing this information on demand to the finite element solver. Because the state of the resin changes dramatically during cure, while that of the reinforcing fibers does not, we employ a unit cell model of the composite material that uses the properties of the constituents to predict both local stresses and effective properties in the composite. The mechanical model, unit cell composite model, and constituent property models are described in more detail in the next three sections.

2.1 Elastic-viscoplastic Model

The mechanical behavior model is based upon a decomposition of the instantaneous strain rate into elastic, viscoplastic, thermal expansion, and cure shrinkage contributions,

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{ij} = \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^E + \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^{VP} + \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^{TH} + \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^{CS} \quad (2)$$

The elastic contribution is related to the stress rate through the usual elastic relationships, with properties that are dependent upon temperature and degree of cure through the reduced temperature. The viscoplastic component is a permanent strain, controlled by the stress, current viscosity, and reduced temperature. The thermal expansion strain is different from most similar models, which treat thermal expansion as being controlled by the difference between the current temperature and a fixed

stress-free reference temperature. We postulate that when the temperature approaches or exceeds the current glass transition temperature, the residual stresses associated with departure from a stress-free temperature are eliminated by viscous relaxation; that is, when the temperature approaches T_g , the viscosity drops, and all or part of the existing thermal strains relax, moving the stress-free reference temperature toward the current temperature at the point. For this reason, the thermal expansion strain is best expressed in rate form, since it no longer represents a conventional thermal strain of the form $\alpha(T - T_{REF})$. The cure shrinkage strain is a volumetric shrinkage, that occurs as a result of the crosslinking reaction, and is tied to the rate of change in degree of cure. Therefore, the shrinkage strain behaves much like a conventional thermal free expansion strain, but is tied to the degree of crosslinking rather than the temperature; therefore, it represents a *permanent* deformation of the polymer, since the reaction is irreversible. The decomposition of the strain rate for each material constituent is similar, but the viscoplastic and cure shrinkage contributions are absent in the reinforcing fibers.

The viscoplastic strain rate contribution is derived from a potential function $\Phi(\sigma)$,

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^{VP} = \frac{1}{\eta} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} \quad (3)$$

In the resin, we use a potential based on the second invariant of the deviatoric stress σ'_{ij} ,

$$\Phi(\sigma_{ij}) = \frac{1}{n} [f(\sigma_{ij})]^n = \frac{1}{n} \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{2} \sigma'_{ij} \sigma'_{ij}} \right)^n = \frac{1}{n} \bar{\sigma}^n \quad (4)$$

The resulting viscoplastic strain rate tensor is

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^{VP} = \frac{3}{2} \frac{\bar{\sigma}^{n-1}}{\eta} \frac{\sigma'_{ij}}{\sqrt{\frac{3}{2} \sigma'_{mn} \sigma'_{mn}}} = \frac{3}{2} \frac{\dot{\bar{\epsilon}}^{VP}}{\bar{\sigma}} \sigma'_{ij} \quad (5)$$

The scalar $\dot{\bar{\epsilon}}^{VP} = \bar{\sigma}^{n-1} / \eta$ is the effective viscoplastic strain rate, and $\bar{\sigma}$ is the von Mises stress. Note that the definition of the viscosity η depends upon the order (n) of the potential function. For $n = 2$, the viscoplastic strain rates are linear in the stress, although the flow rule is nonlinear due to the dependence of the viscosity on temperature and degree of cure.

The thermal expansion and cure shrinkage coefficients are obtained from material response data by analyzing the rate of change in specific volume with temperature and degree of cure, namely

$$\frac{1}{V} \frac{dV}{dt} = \frac{1}{V} \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial T} \right)_x \dot{T} + \frac{1}{V} \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial X} \right)_T \dot{X} = \alpha_{VOL} \dot{T} + \beta_{VOL} \dot{X} \quad (6)$$

The coefficients of thermal expansion and cure shrinkage so obtained are *tangential* values, rather than the *secant* coefficients typically employed in finite element computations. This choice is intentional, for reasons mentioned earlier. The resulting system of mechanical constitutive equations at a material point, for each of the constituent materials, is then

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = C_{ijmn} (\dot{\epsilon}_{mn} - \dot{\epsilon}_{mn}^{VP} - \dot{\epsilon}_{mn}^{TH} - \dot{\epsilon}_{mn}^{CS}) \quad (7a)$$

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{mn}^{VP} = \frac{3}{2} \frac{\bar{\sigma}^{n-2}}{\eta} \sigma'_{mn} ; \quad \dot{\epsilon}_{mn}^{TH} = \alpha_{mn} \dot{T} ; \quad \dot{\epsilon}_{mn}^{CS} = \beta_{mn} \dot{X} \quad (7b)$$

In Equation 7(a-b), the instantaneous elasticity coefficients for an isotropic constituent material are

$$C_{ijmn} = (K - \frac{2}{3}G) \delta_{ij} \delta_{mn} + G(\delta_{im} \delta_{jn} + \delta_{in} \delta_{jm}) \quad (8)$$

with the bulk and shear moduli (K, G) both dependent upon reduced temperature. Typically the resin is nominally isotropic, while the reinforcing fiber may be transversely isotropic. The remaining property coefficients η , $\alpha_{mn} = \frac{1}{3} \alpha_{VOL} \delta_{mn}$, and $\beta_{mn} = \frac{1}{3} \beta_{VOL} \delta_{mn}$, also depend upon reduced temperature, which reflects both the current temperature and degree of cure.

The mechanical constitutive equations for both resin and fiber must be solved simultaneously, enforcing the appropriate compatibility conditions between the motions of both constituents. This solution can be done approximately using well-known methods [8], or numerically using techniques such as finite elements or the method of cells [9]. We choose to perform the solution using a unit cell finite element model at each material point. The unit cell solution can be refined if necessary, provides useful information about stresses and deformations in the constituent materials, and eliminates the need for some challenging effective property calculations, notably CTE [10].

2.2 Unit Cell Material Point Model

Our finite element simulation of the processing event uses an *implicit* solution procedure, which solves a nonlinear system of equations at each increment of time to advance the solution. The analyses reported herein use a coupled temperature-displacement solution, in which the mechanical equilibrium conditions, the heat balance equations, and the material constitutive equations (reaction kinetics, heat generation, thermal properties, thermal expansion, cure shrinkage, and plastic flow) are solved simultaneously, accounting for interactions between these phenomena as the solution unfolds. The solution of the overall system uses a Newton-Raphson iteration, in which out-of-balance forces and heat flows are brought to equilibrium iteratively, with each iteration involving a matrix solution of the complete system. The material point equations provide two important pieces of information to the overall solution: first, they apply the constitutive model and report response quantities, such as stress and heat flux, needed to form the residuals of the balance equations; secondly, they supply the gradients of these quantities, which help form the coefficient matrices that are solved at each iteration cycle. The accuracy of this gradient information has a dramatic effect on the rate of convergence of the iterative solution. Since a typical processing simulation involves on the order of a thousand solution cycles, rapid convergence of the iterations is highly desirable.

The material point unit cell finite element (UCFE) model, which performs the calculation of stress and gradient (mechanical property) information, is a small finite element model established at each integration point of the larger finite element model. In a model of 100,000 elements, using $2 \times 2 \times 2$ Gaussian quadrature, there are 800,000 of these unit cell models, each recording and analysing the state of an individual material point within the overall finite element mesh. The UCFE model uses the deformation gradient reported by Abaqus at the point to generate boundary conditions, and solves for the detailed deformation state and stress distribution in the unit cell. The UCFE model contains only enough detail to describe a “general” unit of the composite material, which in this case consists of a fiber surrounded by matrix material (Figure 1). Boundary conditions applied to the UCFE model are consistent with the continuum deformation gradient, but allow for local deformation of the constituent materials on a smaller scale. Traction determined from the unit cell solution are integrated over the exterior element faces and averaged to provide nominal stress information to the overall finite element calculation. The final stiffness coefficients in the UCFE model also provide the material stiffness to Abaqus for use in forming the element tangent stiffness matrices.

Figure 1: Unit cell finite element models using rectangular and general geometry.

Efficiency of the UCFE solution is a concern, since a cure process simulation requires a number of unit cell solutions equal to the product of the number of integration points in the complete model and the number of solution iteration cycles, on the order of 10^8 – 10^9 solutions. Since the unit cell geometry depends only upon material volume fractions, and does not change significantly during the simulation, many of the usual calculations required in a finite element solution – element and surface geometry

calculations, the shape functions and integrals of their products, bookkeeping tables, and more – can be precomputed and embedded in the solution routines as data, which are loaded prior to execution. Currently, the code contains embedded unit cell data for 3×3×1, 4×4×2, and 6×6×2 rectangular unit cell models, and models of general shape.

The precomputed finite element array structure uses a reorganization of the discretized weak form for an element first proposed by Gupta and Mohraz [11] and later generalized to nonlinear systems by the first author [12]. Every contribution to the element coefficient matrices can be written in terms of a linear combination of outer products of shape functions and shape function derivatives,

$$\mathbf{K}^{(u_i, u_j)} = \sum_{m=0}^3 \sum_{n=0}^3 c_{mn}^{ij} \int_{V_e} \mathbf{N}_{,x_m} \mathbf{N}_{,x_n}^T dV_e \quad (9)$$

where $m=0$ and $n=0$ are interpreted as shape functions with no derivatives taken. The coefficients c_{mn}^{ij} depend upon material properties and, for large-deformation problems, terms in the deformation gradient. Since the temperature and degree of cure at a material point are constant for the unit cell, the coefficients are constant and the above arrays may be precomputed and combined using the current properties as required.

2.3 Resin Constituent Material Property Models (Thermomechanical and Chemical Kinetics)

The mechanical and thermomechanical properties of the resin all are cast in terms of the reduced temperature T_r (Equation 1), which reflects both the temperature and degree of cure at a point in a useful way. For the toughened epoxy material used in this study, Cycom® 5320-1, experimental data for the modulus, viscosity, coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE), and cure shrinkage collapse nicely when represented in terms of T_r as an independent variable. In general, the interpretation of data for each of these parameters is quite challenging, since every test involves a continuous, irreversible change in the material state, which must be modeled accurately as part of the data reduction process.

Figure 2 shows the four principal mechanical and thermomechanical properties as represented in the reduced-temperature models. At temperatures well below glass transition (that is $T_r < 0$), the behavior is glassy (solid-like), with high resistance to elastic and inelastic deformation reflected in high values of the modulus and viscosity, respectively. Above the glass transition is the rubbery region, where the stiffness and viscosity are low, permitting significant deformation at relatively low stress. The higher CTE in the rubbery region also reflects increased compliance there. The cure shrinkage (rate) coefficient has a slightly different interpretation, since the shrinkage occurring at all temperatures reflects irreversible state changes caused by the crosslinking reaction.

Figure 2: Mechanical and thermomechanical properties versus reduced temperature.

The reduced temperature models are listed in Equation 10. The coefficients (a,b,c,d,m) appearing in each model indicate the general form of the model and are defined separately for each property. The piecewise form of the viscosity model reflects the difficulty of obtaining accurate viscosity data outside a relatively narrow range of reduced temperatures centered around the glass transition temperature. Fortunately, the viscosity at the lower end of this range, about -0.3, is large enough to inhibit any significant viscoplastic flow. Temperatures at the upper end of the range in which

experiments can be completed are also not essential to the model, since the material either is in a near-liquid state or, if previously solidified and crosslinked, will experience significant charring.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Modulus} \quad \ln(E) &= \frac{a}{1 + e^{-b(T_r - c)}} + mT_r + d \\
 \text{Viscosity} \quad \log_{10}(\eta) &= \begin{cases} A_{\max} & T_r \leq T_t^0 \\ aT_r^2 + bT_r + c & T_t^0 < T_r \leq T_t^1 \\ A_{\min} & T_r^1 < T_r \end{cases} \\
 \text{Tangent CTE} \quad \alpha &= \frac{1}{3} \left[\frac{a}{1 + e^{-b(T_r - c)}} + mT_r + d \right] \\
 \text{Shrinkage rate} \quad \beta &= \frac{1}{3} \left[\frac{a}{1 + e^{-b(T_r - c)}} + mT_r + d \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

The associated model of the chemical kinetics used in the current study expresses the rate of conversion and the glass transition temperature in terms of the ratio $T_g/T = 1/(T_r + 1)$ (Equation 11).

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Cure rate} \quad \dot{x} &= e^{(QT_g/T+P)} \frac{1}{1 + e^{-b(T_g/T - c)}} (1 - x) \\
 \text{Glass transition} \quad T_g &= \frac{a}{1 + e^{-b(x - c)}} + d
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

The variables (P,Q) refer to lookup table values dependent on degree of cure and temperature.

One distinct advantage of the reduced-temperature models adopted here is that the extensive test matrices required for characterization of the resin are reduced in size rather significantly. Interpretation of the test data, while still not entirely straightforward, is simplified somewhat when working only in terms of the reduced temperature. The next section of the paper describes selected experimental and data reduction procedures for the models in greater detail.

3 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

3.1 Resin Constituent Determination: Modulus and Viscosity

Modulus and viscosity data used to populate the current model are derived from experiments using the Rheometrics Solids Analyzer [13] by TA Instruments (RSA III). The RSA III operates in a controlled strain manner where the actuator applies a deformation, or strain, axially to the specimen, and the transducer measures the resultant force generated by the sample deformation. Specimens of Cycom® 5320-1 were fabricated as thin films of approximate dimensions: 32 mm (1.6 in) long x 10 mm (0.4 in) wide x 0.2 mm (0.008 in) thick. The films were then cured at the appropriate isothermal temperatures for 24 hours to achieve the desired degree of cure. Modulus data are derived from both static and sinusoidal loading (1.5% and 3.0% strain amplitude) for specimens with a range of initial degrees of cure between 0.48 and 1.0. Figure 3 shows a selection of the data for the complete range of degrees of cure and the corresponding model fit to the form indicated in Equation 10.

Figure 3: Modulus data and model fit.

As mentioned in Section 2.3, the viscosity model takes a different form from the modulus, CTE and cure shrinkage models because of the experimental limitations associated with collecting reliable data from the RSA III in the viscoplastic region causing truncation at both high and low reduced temperatures. For the present viscosity model, the most important viscous response characteristics occur for temperatures in the neighborhood of the glass transition (i.e. $T_r = 0$), where the potential for a combination of high modulus and low viscosity exists and can lead to significant creep and stress relief. Our strategy for collecting good data in this region began with fully-cured specimens, and we varied the T_r over the transition region between the glassy and rubbery regimes. Temperatures that were too high lead to degradation of the specimen while temperatures too low lead to excessive instrument compliance [13] resulting from a specimen stiffness outside the instrument's transducer range. Nevertheless, meaningful data was collected by the RSA III over a large enough range of reduced temperatures to define the viscoplastic characteristics of the resin adequately.

Figure 4 shows viscosity data extracted from stress relaxation experiments in the transition region of 5320-1 using fully-cured test specimens. The viscoplastic viscosity parameter is obtained from the changes in both stress and strain over relatively large increments of time (typically 500 seconds). The viscosity was then determined from the test data using the backward Euler time integration as shown.

$$\eta = \frac{E\sigma^{(t+\Delta t)}\Delta t}{E\Delta\varepsilon - \Delta\sigma} \quad (12)$$

In Equation 12, $\sigma^{(t+\Delta t)}$ represents the stress at the end of the interval considered. The curve has been terminated on the left at a viscosity of 1×10^{20} Pa-s to avoid numerical issues. In practical terms the remainder of the left end of the curve is unimportant, since this cutoff viscosity already corresponds to a strain rate of 1×10^{-12} under a 100 MPa stress. Similarly, the details of the far right of the curve are not essential to the model because the modulus is low enough that significant stresses cannot develop.

Figure 4: Viscosity data and model fit for intermediate reduced temperature range.

3.2 Resin Cure Shrinkage and Thermal Expansion Determination

The resin cure shrinkage coefficient and coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) are used to describe the change in dimension (or volume) of the resin during cure reaction as temperature and degree of cure change. Assuming the specific volume of this curing resin is a function of temperature and degree of cure, the temporal derivative can be written as

$$\frac{\dot{V}}{V} = \left(\frac{1}{V} \frac{\partial V}{\partial T} \right)_x \dot{T} + \left(\frac{1}{V} \frac{\partial V}{\partial x} \right)_T \dot{x} = \alpha_v \dot{T} + \beta_v \dot{x} \quad (13)$$

where β_v is the volumetric cure shrinkage coefficient and α_v is the volumetric coefficient of thermal expansion. By carefully designing experiments containing temperature heat-up and cool-down ramps and isothermal holds, the parameters β_v and α_v can be determined. For instance, during an isothermal hold, only the volumetric cure shrinkage of resin is observed, and, therefore, β_v is obtained using the reaction rate predicted by the kinetics model. CTE can be obtained during heating and cooling ramps in periods when the reaction rate is negligible and thermal expansion is the predominant cause of volume change. The leading factors of 1/3 in Equation 10 convert the volumetric coefficients to the linear values used in the mechanical constitutive model.

Dilatometer measurements on Cycom® 5320-1 were performed at the University of Southern Mississippi using a Gnomix PVT dilatometer [14]. An uncured specimen of known initial mass and volume was subjected to a specified temperature cycle employing multiple ramp and hold intervals under a pressure of 10 MPa as imposed by the confining fluid. Figures 5 (a-b) below show the cure shrinkage and CTE data along with the corresponding coefficient model fits extracted from the dilatometer experiments.

Figure 5: Coefficient of thermal expansion data (a), cure shrinkage coefficient data (b), and model fits.

4 RESULTS

Predictions made with the proposed elastic-viscoplastic model are quite encouraging. To date, our validation efforts are based on results of a cure cycle study [13] using a full design of experiments (DoE) matrix with low and high gelation temperatures, fast and slow ramp rates, and integrated versus freestanding postcure processes. The part used in the study is an angle bracket (Figure 6) built from IM7/5320-1 prepreg in a $[+45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ layup. The parts are 152.4 mm (6 in.) long, about 4.064 mm (0.15 in.) thick, with leg length 88.9 mm (3.5 in.). In the experimental study, results of interest included curved beam strength, spring-in angle, porosity and thickness in the bend region, and leg thickness. In validating the analytical predictions, we focus on the spring-in angles for the various cure cycles, which are important in the design of appropriate tooling.

Figure 6. Angle bracket and tool geometry.

Of particular interest in validating the analytical predictions are the differences between integrated and freestanding postcure processes. Increasing interest in OOA processes, for both economic and logistical reasons, demands accurate predictions of dimensional control for these materials and processes. Earlier studies [15,7] suggest that existing cure cycle simulations are capable of reasonable predictions for integrated cure processes but experience difficulty in predicting the behavior resulting from freestanding cure cycles or processing with multiple returns to room temperature. The cure cycle parameters for the DoE matrix are shown in Table 1. The remainder of this section summarizes results of spring-in predictions, trend analysis, and refinement and sensitivity studies related to the angle

bracket experiments.

Cure Cycle	Gel Temp (F)	Ramp Rate	Postcure
1a	93°C (200°F)	fast	integrated
2a	93°C (200°F)	slow	integrated
3a	135°C (275°F)	fast	integrated
4a	135°C (275°F)	slow	integrated
1b	93°C (200°F)	fast	freestanding
2b	93°C (200°F)	slow	freestanding
3b	135°C (275°F)	fast	freestanding
4b	135°C (275°F)	slow	freestanding

Table 1. Cure cycle characteristics.

4.1 Bracket Spring-in Predictions for DOE

Spring-in predictions for the DoE angle bracket specimens have been performed using Abaqus [16,17] and the AFRL-developed UMAT software. All analyses are performed using the coupled temperature-displacement solution procedure in which the heat transfer, chemical kinetics and mechanical equilibrium equations are solved simultaneously. The mesh size used in most of the simulations is limited to about 2 mm; earlier solutions [7] using fewer elements in the legs of the brackets did predict the behavior trends properly but were not sufficiently refined to capture the sharp stress gradients occurring near the free edges. The current models, using one element per layer in the laminate, have 67,200 elements in the bracket and 4,554 elements in the tool with 317,000 total degrees of freedom. In all cases, we have used 8-node hexahedral elements (C3D8T or C3D8RT). For integrated postcures, the simulation consists of four Abaqus *steps* [17]: pressurization (bagging), cure, unloading, and tool removal. Contact between tool and part occurs in the bagging step and is released in the tool removal step. For freestanding postcures, 7 steps are used: bagging, on-tool cure, cooling, unloading, tool removal, freestanding postcure, and cooling.

Figure 7 shows a comparison of measured and predicted spring-in angles for the DoE cure cycles. The measured spring-in angles are small due to the relative simplicity of the part. Measurement error is around 0.10 degree. The predicted spring-in angles exhibit about half a degree error on average, and the relative magnitude of the spring-in angles for any pair of cure cycles is represented quite well. A difference in errors does exist between the integrated and freestanding cure cycles, with the integrated cycles averaging about 0.65 degree error, and the freestanding cycles about 0.40 degrees. One disadvantage of using a single specimen type for validation is that it is impossible to ascertain whether these errors are absolute or relative in nature. In general, predictions that lie within roughly one-half degree of actual values and predict the relative deformation resulting from numerous processing cycles correctly would be considered quite good and valuable to aid in the tooling engineer's design process.

Figure 7. Measured and predicted spring-in angles for DoE cure cycle angle bracket specimens.

4.2 Solution Trends and Sensitivity

This section addresses the analysis of trends predicted for the angle bracket specimen series, as well as sensitivity and convergence studies conducted, to provide a better understanding of the model behavior and parameter sensitivity. Opportunities for errors and inconsistencies abound in simulating a process as complex as composite processing. Developing an awareness of which predicted results are most reliable, and which may be suspect, may be as important as the simulation process itself.

4.2.1 Solution Trends for Angle Bracket

Figures 8-10 show the trends of behavior associated with each of the principal DoE process variables: cure cycle type, gelation temperature, and ramp rate. In each plot, all eight cycles are shown, with one value of the variable of interest at the left of the plot, and the second value at the right end. Measured spring-in values are shown as solid lines, and predictions are in dashed lines, with each combination of the remaining two variables plotted in a different color. For example, in the cure cycle type plot (Figure 8), the green lines each show the trend of increase/decrease in spring-in caused by a change in the cure cycle type, for the combination (fast ramp rate, high gelation temperature). Each line of a different color shows a different combination of these two remaining variables. Therefore, the quality of the predicted trends can be evaluated by comparing the slope of the solid and dashed lines of the same color. If each pair of same-colored lines has the same slope, then the effect of the variable on the horizontal axis has been captured correctly for the other process parameters.

Figure 8. Spring-in trends versus cure cycle type.

Figure 9. Spring-in trends versus gelation temperature.

Figure 10. Spring-in trends versus temperature ramp rate.

The spring-in trends predicted using the elastic-viscoplastic model are quite good, and the effect of each of the DoE process variables is represented well. The difference between average errors for the integrated and freestanding cycles is evident in Figure 8 where the slope of the modeled results (dashed lines) is less steep than that in the measured data (solid lines).

4.2.2 Convergence/Mesh Refinement on Bracket

To date, we have not performed a formal convergence study on the overall finite element model, although such a study is planned for the near future. However, we have employed both graded meshes and nearly-uniform meshes for the same predictions, with interesting results. The graded meshes are similar to the uniform mesh in the bend area of the bracket, with element sizes of approximately 2 mm; the mesh is coarsened near the ends of the flat legs, with element sizes of 9 mm at the free edge. The resulting model is much smaller (21,120 elements in the bracket, as compared with 67,200 for the uniform model). Despite the fact that the legs are flat and the layup constant, the coarser model fails to capture the high stress gradients that occur near the ends of the legs. Examination of the section forces near the ends of the legs reveals significant differences in the stresses, resulting in opposite curvatures in the legs between the two solutions for some cure cycles. In terms of the spring-in predictions, the coarser model, whose level of detail appears quite reasonable, exhibits an average error in spring-in for the freestanding cure cycles of 0.74 degrees, as opposed to 0.40 degrees for the finer model.

4.2.3 Additional Sensitivity Studies

Further studies in progress with the current process simulation model include the effect of unit cell geometry (rectangular versus round-shaped fibers), unit cell model refinement, estimates of effective (composite) CTE for various unit cell models, as compared with commonly used composite models [10], and uncertainty in the degree of cure estimation. This last item is particularly relevant because of the need to employ at least an approximate cure kinetics model during nearly all property data reduction for the resin material. For the 5320-1 resin, our rough estimates of the possible error in determination of the degree of cure are in the neighbourhood of ± 5 percent, which produces a correspondingly large uncertainty in both property values and response predictions.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A new mechanical model for use in predicting residual stresses and deformations resulting from the curing of a reinforced composite has been developed. Preliminary versions of the model have been shown to predict behavior trends correctly for changes in important cure cycle parameters (gelation temperature, ramp rate, and postcure type). The premise of the model is that viscoplastic flow is the primary time-dependent mechanism leading to relaxation of process-induced residual stresses at cure cycle temperatures near the material's glass transition temperature. The model employs several material submodels based on reduced temperature, which reflects the effect of both temperature and degree of cure on the state of the material, simplifying the collection and interpretation of experimental material response data. The system of models has been implemented and tested using Cycom® 5320-

1, a toughened epoxy resin suitable for out-of-autoclave processing. Validation of the model and associated data has been performed for spring-in prediction using a full DoE series of angle bracket specimens as well as for sensitivity studies on the unit cell and overall finite element models.

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